

Speculation on Dirac Spinors

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 3. 2024

The Dirac spinor formalism emerges from linearizing $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ with $E = \hbar \partial/\partial t$ partial and $p = -\hbar \nabla$ grad partial and is often described in the literature (1).

Here, we attempt to argue that the forms of the matrices which appear are due to the basic asymmetry of time and x in the case of m_0 (rest mass) > 0 . In particular, in the rest frame, t is a running variable and x is a fixed one and one immediately sees the asymmetry. This carries over to the equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ in which two terms are linked with the time or fourth component of the 4-vector and only one with the spatial ones. This asymmetry is further seen in the resolutions \hbar/p and \hbar/E . It is only in the case of the photon that these are the same ($c=1$) and in such a case, one does not use Dirac formalism.

We thus suggest as a starting point an asymmetry in t and x . This means that if one linearizes $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$), and assumes only one spatial direction at first (say x), then one requires matrices for anticommutation. Given that t exists in the rest frame and one only has a clock ticking in this frame (linked to $\partial/\partial t$), t is a stand-alone variable which we argue should be linked with the identity matrix (2×2 being the smallest) which yields the eigenvalue 1 for all 2 basis vectors. This is equivalent to nothing happening except a clock ticking, we argue. Given the identity matrix, one cannot have it anticommute with another 2×2 matrix, so one needs 4 dimensions and two sets of 2×2 matrices. The three matrices for x, y, z must have the same structure with respect to the 2×2 I and $-I$ 2×2 along the diagonal. In other words, these have a 2×2 matrix and its negative along the antidiagonal.

The point we wish to make is that even for just an x direction, the 2×2 matrix chosen (appearing twice, once with a factor of 1, another time with -1 in the 4×4 matrix) should have two eigenvalues (as it does). Thus, the breaking of symmetry between t and x for $m_0 > 0$ leads to a breaking in the behaviour of the 2×2 matrices linked with E (or t) and p (or x). Given that d/dx represents motion in the x -direction, it seems that the 2×2 matrix linked with x is not directly describing motion in the x direction, but with two other degrees of freedom.

We have suggested in previous notes that these might be the z and y directions, i.e. spin in two directions about the x axis as an analogy. The point we wish to make is that the matrix for t and that for x are very different and we ascribe this to the different resolutions \hbar/E and \hbar/p , i.e. the asymmetry between t and x for $m_0 > 0$. In other words, space-time with ct and x being on the same footing holds for a photon. Given that $E=pc$ for a photon, one does not see spin until one uses equations with the electric and magnetic fields (i.e. a continuity equation with energy and momentum Poynting density). Thus, for the photon, it seems that an x - t view of the picture is fine with x lying in the direction of p . For a particle with $m_0 > 0$, such a view is not fine. The asymmetry of t, x forces two extra degrees of freedom into the picture (i.e. the 2 eigenvalues of the 2×2 matrix linked with x ($p(x)$)). Given the Stern-Gerlach experiment, it seems that these two degrees of freedom are somehow linked to the two extra axes in addition to x . In other words, the asymmetry not only splits t from x , but causes t to be split from x and two other degrees of freedom, possibly y and z .

Dirac Spinors

One may formally obtain Dirac 4x4 matrices and spinor 4 vectors (2 sets of 2 vectors) by solving the problem of linearizing:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{with } E = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \text{ and } p = -i\hbar \text{ grad} \quad ((1))$$

as done in (1).

$$\text{Specifically, one has: } (B i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + A \cdot p - mI) W(x,t) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

((2)) shows that one needs matrices for B,A with I being the identity matrix and that these matrices must anticommute.

The full solution is shown in (1) to be:

$$\begin{pmatrix} | I & 0 & | & | 0 & s_x & | & | 0 & s_y & | & | 0 & s_z & \\ | 0 & -1 & | & | -s_x & 0 & | & | -s_y & 0 & | & | -s_z & 0 & \end{pmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

We wish to point out the symmetry of the form of the three spatial matrixes (using s_x, s_y, s_z) and their difference with I, the 2x2 identity matrix. This occurs because x, y, z are on the same footing, but t is not. For a photon, one has space time, but for a particle with rest mass, there is symmetry breaking between t and the x, y, z co-ordinates. We argue that this idea governs the form of ((3)) which is normally presented as simply a math solution to ((2)).

Asymmetry Between t and x For $m_0 > 0$

If m_0 (rest mass) > 0 , then there exists a rest frame such that m_0 sits at $x=0$ (example), but t is a running variable. Thus, there is asymmetry between t and x and t is the only running variable in this frame. If one shifts to a moving frame, then: $-Et + px = \text{invariant}$ and $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$). In such a case, the asymmetry between t and x should persist and one sees from $-Et + px = A$, that $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar / p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar / E$ yield degenerate A values, but the t and x resolutions differ. Such is not the case for a photon ($c=1$).

We thus argue that the asymmetry between t and x, y, z should carry over to the matrices used in ((2)). In fact, we argue that in the rest frame nothing happens except the clicking of the clock so we suggest that t is somehow linked with an identity matrix.

It is known that B and A must be matrices in ((2)) and must anticommute. The smallest matrix for time is the 2x2 identity, but this does not commute with other 2x2 matrices. One should try:

$$\begin{pmatrix} | I (2x2) & 0 & \\ | 0 & -I (2x2) & \end{pmatrix} \quad ((4))$$

The form for the three spatial matrixes must be the same because they are of the same nature (spatial co-ordinates), hence the form of the last three matrixes in ((3)).

One may next note that I (2×2) has a degenerate eigenvalue of 1 for $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$. In other words, id/dt partial describes the resolution of the clock and nothing else happens.

S_x , s_y and s_x must differ from the identity matrix because time and space are asymmetric for $m_0 > 0$, we argue. We suggest that this difference appears in the form of two eigenvalues.

Next, consider only one direction in space, say x . id/dt describes changes in time with resolution \hbar/E and $-id/dx$, changes in space with resolution \hbar/p . These are asymmetric, but now the existence of two eigenvalues of the matrix s_x associated with x suggested two extra degrees of freedom. (Note: One may show by explicitly calculating s_x, s_y, s_z , the Pauli matrices which are 2×2 matrices which anticommute that they have two eigenvalues..).

Where are these two degrees of freedom? We have suggested in previous notes that the y, z axes are candidates even for x motion only. (This seems to be born out by the Stern Gerlach experiment.) In other words, the asymmetry of t and x and the existence of t in the rest mass forces t to be linked with the 2×2 identity matrix and this in turn forces x (or the x component of p) to be linked with a matrix with two eigenvalues, or in other words the y, z axes (or maybe some kind of rotational motion describing the two axes to describe the Stern Gerlach experiment, although this is not simple rotation.)

Thus, the breaking of symmetry between t and x seems to force the notion of t with three spatial co-ordinates and not one. Thus, even if one postulated a one-dimensional space, the asymmetry of t and x suggests that there must be two other dimensions, y and z ., we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine Dirac matrices and spinors from the point of view of t - x symmetry breaking for $m_0 > 0$. In particular, in the rest frame, one has a ticking clock and only a t running variable. Nothing else seems to happen. We thus suggest an identity matrix (the smallest being 2×2) to be associated with time (or E) in the linearized form $EE = pp + m_0 m_0$, i.e. ((2)). The identity matrix does not anticommute with other 2×2 matrices, so one requires a 4×4 matrix with $I(2 \times 2)$ and $-I(2 \times 2)$ along the diagonal. This then requires the same form of anticommuting matrices for x, y, z , namely s_i and $-s_i$ along the antidiagonals.

$I(2 \times 2)$ only has one eigenvalue, but one may show that s_x, s_y, s_z have two, meaning that now there are two degrees of freedom. In other words, if one imagines a t and a one-dimensional space x , the antisymmetry between t and x seems to force an additional two degrees of freedom on x , which we suggest are linked to the axes y, z . Thus, t - x antisymmetry for $m_0 > 0$ seems to force the notion of 3-space for $m_0 > 0$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dirac_equation

